

STUDY OF DIGITAL LITERACY OF STUDENT TEACHERS

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Abstract

Digital literacy refers to an individual's ability to find evaluate, and clearly communicate information through typing and other media on various digital platforms. It is evaluated by an individual's grammar, composition, typing skills and ability to produce text, images, audio and designs using technology. Focus of this paper is to find the level of Digital literacy of student's teachers. In this study survey method has used and self-constructed questionnaire is used as tool for data collection. The finding of the study showed there is no significant difference in Digital literacy of Male and female student-teachers. There is significant difference in Digital literacy of English and Marathi Medium student-teachers.

Keywords-*Digital, Digital literacy, student teachers*

Introduction-

Present era is technology era .everyone use technology so much in our daily life that the internet is one of the basic necessities today. The Internet makes it easy to use advanced technology. In today's technology. In today's technological age, the term digital literacy has just emerged. Right now; every citizen is getting connected to the internet world. It requires a certain computer language and some technical issues and concepts, without which it is impossible for you to become digitally literate easily. The whole world has come closer because of the internet. Given the growing use of the internet, if the majority of people could use it we would see a different internet world. For this, in the future, all people need to be digitally literate. At present we are constantly hearing the concept of digital India. Every essential commodity and service is available online. Similarly, at the level of online education and social medial to has become a necessity for us to be able use our mobile or computer properly.

The average person uses mobile internet for at least two threw to eight ten hours from waking up in the morning to going to bed at night .therefore, online shopping for essentials, banking facilities, television facilities, health facilities, online education as well as online booking for travel have become easy for people. The goal a few years ago was to make all

citizens literate. But now with mobile, computer and internet, the goal is make people digitally literate. Technology is making human life more convenient and healthier day by day .As part of that, the concept of digital literacy must be implemented everywhere. Advances in science and technology have enabled us to create electronic resources such as mobiles, Computer and laptops. The ability to fully utilize the same resources is called “digital literacy”. Digital literacy is the ability of a person to find, evaluate and write clear information through writing and other means omnivorous digital plat forms. The American Library Association (ALA) defines digital literacy as “the ability to use information and communications technology to discover, evaluate, create, and communicate information that requires cognitive and technical skills.” Overall, digital literacy shares a numbers of principles defined with other fields that are ways to use modifiers in front of literacy and define domain specific knowledge or abilities. The term has grown in popularity in education and higher education settings and is used both internationally and nationally.it is hoped that digital literacy will lead to active participation in democracy and development, as well as increase their employment.

Need and Importance of Study

The present research is necessary to know the level of Digital literacy of student teachers. The research presented is based on the current situation and the future era is going to be completely digital. With this in mind, it is imperative for all future teachers who are undergoing teacher training today to be digitally literate. The importance of digital literacy is emphasized in the new educational policy the researcher hopes that this training program will be important for future teachers to be digitally literate. Understanding and using digital literacy technology is important. Digital literacy skills help you to find, use and create information online in a productive and useful way. Only with an understanding and knowledge of digital literacy can you be able to use technology safely and avoid its dangers. So having digital literacy is very important.

Operational definition-

1 **Student- Teacher** – Student who learns in College of Education, B.Ed. College student who acquires the skills required to become a school teacher.

2 **Digital Literacy** –smart Phone, Tab, smart board, Mobile, computer and laptop etc.: Using it to create instructional lessons, easy access to social media, audio and video creation, account creation on your own various web sites, easy access to computers, internet and digital

equipment, learning computer skills. Online conversations with others and respect for digital assets etc., are called digital literacy.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The statement of the problem is as follows:

A study of Digital literacy of student teachers

Objectives of the study

1. To check the current status of digital literacy among student- teachers of pune district.
2. To study the significance difference among the following categories with reference to digital literacy.(Male and female, English medium and Marathi medium student teachers.)

Hypothesis.

1. There will be significant difference between the level of digital literacy of male and female student- teachers.
2. There will be significant difference between the level of digital literacy of digital literacy of Marathi and English medium student- teachers.

Null Hypothesis.

1. There will be no significant difference between the level of digital literacy of male and female student- teachers.
2. There will be no significant difference between the level of digital literacy of digital literacy of Marathi and English medium student- teachers.

Research method-Researcher has used survey method in the present research for the study of leadership qualities of secondary students.

Population and sample

Population- All student teacher from college of education in Pune District

Sample of the Research:

86 student teacher from college of education from Pune district. Purposive sampling method used.

Data Collection Tool-Researcher used Questionnaire for data collection in this present research.

Statistical Techniques: Researcher used statistical techniques Mean, SD, T-Test for analysis of data.

Scope and limitation of the study –

Scope-present research related to student teachers digital literacy

Limitation 1. The study is restricted only to Pune district. 2. The study is restricted only to B.Ed. colleges. 3. The study is restricted only to B.Ed. student teachers.

Interpretation-

Table 1-Male and female student teachers digital literacy level

Gender	N	Mean
Male	46	171.8
Female	40	169.88

Male student teachers digital literacy mean is 171.8 .male student teachers digital literacy level is good. Female student teachers digital literacy mean is 169.88.female student teachers digital literacy level is good.

Graph No-1Male and female student teacher digital literacy

Table 2-Male and female student teachers digital literacy level

Medium	N	Mean
Marathi	46	159.0889
English	40	169.5

Marathi medium student teachers digital literacy mean is 159.08.Marathi medium student teachers digital literacy level is satisfactory. And English medium student teachers digital literacy mean is 169.5.English medium student teachers digital literacy level is good.

Graph No-2 Marathi medium and English medium student teachers digital literacy

Hypothesis-1

There will be no significant difference between the level of digital literacy of male and female student- teachers.

Table N0.3 Digital literacy of Male and female student-teachers.

Gender	N	Mean	SD	t-ratio	remarks
Male	46	171.8	9.79	1.03	Accepted
Female	40	169.88	8.2		

(At 0.05% level of significance, the table value 't' is 1.96)

It is inferred from the table 1 that the calculated value of 't' is 1.03 which is less than the table value of 't'(1.96) at 0.05% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. It means there is no significant difference in Digital literacy of Male and female student-teachers.

Hypothesis-2

There will be no significant difference between the level of digital literacy of digital literacy of Marathi and English medium student- teachers.

Table N0.4 Digital literacy of English and Marathi Medium student-teachers.

Medium	N	Mean	SD	t-ratio	remarks
Marathi	46	159.0889	11.91413	4.62	Reject
English	40	169.5	8.6		

(At 0.05% level of significance, the table value 't' is 1.96)

It is inferred from the table 1 that the calculated value of 't' is 4.62 which is more than the table value of 't'(1.96) at 0.05% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. It means there is significant difference in Digital literacy of English and Marathi Medium student-teachers.

Conclusion-

Digital literacy level of student-teachers is good.

Digital literacy level of Male and female student teachers are good.

Digital literacy level of English medium students is good

Digital literacy level of Marathi medium student teacher is satisfactory

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